

THE METHODS OF TEACHERS WORKING WITH STUDENTS PLAY A CRUCIAL ROLE IN ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Annotation: This article demonstrates the processes through which teachers interact with their students. It discusses what a teacher should be like, the principles they should follow while working with students, the image they should project, and the characteristics they should possess. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of maintaining composure while working with students, illustrated through various examples.

Keywords: teachers, their characteristics, their images, pupils, methods, projects.

INTRODUCTION

The educational process is an activity based on collaboration between teachers and students, in which personal development, knowledge, and upbringing are realized. The teacher conveys their knowledge and skills to students during lessons, while students assimilate this knowledge and develop the ability to apply it in practice. In the learning process, students use various methods to receive, process, and apply information, developing their unique approaches.

The goals of education are shaped according to the needs of society, and the objectives of education and upbringing must be coordinated with each other. Scientific literature includes aspects such as developing correct and precise skills, enhancing logical and creative thinking, instilling national ideals, and enriching the individual spiritually. In this process, students' independent thinking abilities, verbal and written literacy, as well as their communication culture are improved. Additionally, opportunities are created to bring students closer to the cultural and ethical values of the nation within the educational process. According to great thinkers, providing good education to future generations is crucial. The reforms being implemented in our country's education system aim for long-term changes and are related to our president's concern for the future generations.

The application of advanced pedagogical approaches and new information technologies not only enhances the effectiveness of educational activities but also plays a significant role in nurturing independent and logically thinking individuals. Through this process, the comprehensive development of the younger generation is ensured. Lessons are given a positive result if it is used in the lessons of repetition or strengthening appointments. The choice of each type of play is the level of education, their level of knowledge, the ability to independent creative performance, the gangs of how well creativity is formed in the memory should be a shared.

The attention is paid to the consideration of a student in education, considering the opinion of others, and the culture of a developed personality is the key to develop the developed personality The position is occupied. The lifestyle of the nation, the cultural structure is studied on the basis of its rich historical heritage.

Today's teacher requires the use of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the educational process. Based on the above, we state our thoughts on the ways to educate the use of interactive methods in classes. We think that it provides practical assistance to our colleagues in increasing the efficiency of training. They will also become one of the close assistants in fulfilling students responsible and preparation for their direction and forming skills of preparation for independent living. We issue recommendations on the implementation of modern methods of training on the basis of classes in classes. You will use it creatively and: "Let's find out what we want to awaken the feelings of pride and buttache to our children," [1], - we hope that you make sure you will achieve the goal by applying modern methods of education and education in response to the lessons.

CONCLUSION

The teacher should like to be cruel, and students are a flower. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to each of them, as if they are sending flowers separately. If they are given less, they will retain their own, and they will pass in the direction they did not want. Therefore, the teacher must be ready for everything for those teachers, and we must give the same affection for each of them, so that we will achieve our own and bring a real teacher and reserve the teacher.

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